

Relevance of Matthew Arnold: Liberal Humanism in Present Context

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Abstract

Matthew Arnold, a very influential poet and critic of the Victorian era, pioneered liberal humanism as a philosophy that advocates engagement with culture and literature necessary on the path to perfection. This paper is an attempt to study the relevance of Arnold's philosophy of liberal humanism in the present time, when the society, on the path of globalization, is going through a rapid evolution as a result of technological advancement and digitalization. Although Arnold's ideas originate from his critique of mid-nineteenth century English society and education, — a society that was going through cultural and moral crisis, — they are still significant. The researcher examines the core tenets of Arnold's liberal humanism, placing them within historical, socio-cultural and educational contexts, and explores their relevance in the contemporary scenario as we see a marked shift in cultural paradigms across the world. It would be worthwhile to revisit Arnold's ideas and ascertain how far they can meet the current challenges in the realm of democracy, culture and education.

Keywords Liberal Humanism, Perfection, Best Self, Democracy, Culture, Education, etc.

Introduction

Matthew Arnold (1822-1888) was an eminent poet, critic, and educationist of the Victorian era. He pioneered liberal humanism as a philosophy that advocates engagement with culture and literature necessary on the path to perfection. *Culture and Anarchy* (1869), his seminal work, enunciates his idea of culture as "a study of perfection" which aims to disseminate and make current among all the three English classes — the barbarians, the philistines, and the populace — "the best which has been thought and said in the world". (Arnold ix) Although Arnold's ideas originate from his critique of mid-nineteenth century English society and education, — a society that was increasingly given to materialism consequent upon scientific and technological advancement and rapid industrialisation and which was going through cultural and moral crisis, — they are still significant in meeting the challenges faced by the contemporary world. This paper is an attempt to study the relevance of Arnold's philosophy of liberal humanism in the present time, when the society, on the path of globalization, is going through a rapid evolution because of technological advancement and digitalization. The researcher examines the core tenets of Arnold's liberal humanism, placing them within historical, socio-cultural and educational contexts, and explores their relevance in the contemporary scenario as we see a marked shift in cultural paradigms across the world. His ideas can provide a powerful framework for educators and policy makers who seek to strike an equilibrium between STEM fields and humanistic education, thereby leading to harmonious and all-round development of all the faculties of individuals contributing to personal as well as societal upliftment. It would be worthwhile to revisit Arnold's ideas and ascertain how far they can meet the current challenges in the realm of democracy, culture and education.

Objective of study

1. To analyse the core tenets of Matthew Arnold's liberal humanism.
2. To assess the potential of Arnold's ideas in addressing the current challenges in the sphere of culture, education and democracy.

Research Questions

1. What are the core tenets of Matthew Arnold's liberal humanism?
2. How can Arnold's ideas be adapted to address the current challenges in the sphere of culture, education and democracy?

Review of Literature

1. "Culture and Anarchy and Other Writings" (1993) edited by Stefan Collini offers a critical insight into Matthew Arnold's Culture and Anarchy and other seminal essays, exploring interrelation between culture, education and democracy. It asserts the humanising power of culture which alone could bring order and peace in chaos-ridden mid-Victorian England consequent upon rapidly growing materialism. The book highlights how similar concerns continue to resonate in succeeding eras and enhances our perception of Arnold's broader intellectual, moral and societal concerns.
2. "Matthew Arnold and English Education: The Poet's Pioneering Advocacy in middle Class Instruction" (2005) by Brendan A. Rapple critically evaluates Arnold's contribution as Inspector of schools in giving direction to much needed educational reforms in mid-nineteenth century England, enabling access of education to all classes, particularly the middle class. Underscoring Arnold's belief in liberal humanistic education as a means of cultural and moral upliftment, the book offers insight into his vision that shaped the education in modern England.
3. "The Interpretations of Cultures" (1973) by Clifford Geertz is a seminal work in cultural anthropology that significantly bridged the gap between anthropology and humanities by emphasizing on meaning and narrative and underlining the symbolic and interpretative aspects of cultural and social practices in varied contexts.

Main Text**Core Tenets of Arnold's Liberal Humanism**

Arnold built his concept of liberal humanism on certain ideas which are still relevant to contemporary discourse on culture and education.

At the centre of Arnold's concept of liberal humanism is his idea that culture stands for man's endless and strenuous journey towards perfection. He defines culture in these words:

"...all the love of our neighbour, the impulses towards action, help, and beneficence, the desire for stopping human error, clearing human confusion, and diminishing the sum of human misery, the noble aspiration to leave the world better and happier than we found it,— motives eminently such as are called social,— come in as part of the grounds of culture, and the main and pre-eminent part...it is a study of perfection." (Arnold 8).

Human beings possess two kinds of selves— ordinary self and best self. Most of the human beings are concerned only about their ordinary or lower self— a narrowly defined personal self— which is associated with routine mundane affairs, and which needs the fulfilment of material and carnal desires for gratification. They pay little heed to the demands of the best or larger self— a widely defined personal self, extending and merging into the social one— which is associated with moral and spiritual development. Arnold was convinced that culture, through engagement with the finest achievements of human thought and art, could enable man to break the confines of his ordinary self and smoothen his voyage towards best self. The limitations of lower self could be conquered by man only when he developed moral insight and learnt to appreciate true beauty, the one that is transcendental in nature. In present time when man is engrossed in superficial entertainment and given to finding surface solutions to the problems that surround him, problems that are getting more and more complex in this digital era, culture is the only means to counterbalance the distractions of superficial diversions and to develop a deeper understanding to these problems. When man devotes time to his best self, — reads a classic book, listens to classical music, indulges in painting or some other form of art, — he engages himself in the process of refining and elevating his best self. This refinement and elevation of the best or inner self gradually permeates into his lower self and is reflected in his outer self through his behaviour.

Another core element of Arnold's concept of liberal humanism is his belief in the autonomy and timelessness of literary texts. Arnold believed that all great works of art and literature carry an inherent meaning below their surface. When one approaches the text with focus and dedication, layers of meanings are uncovered, and one comes to know the universal truths that transcend time and space, the truths that go beyond historical and sociological contexts. His belief in this idea and propagation of the same later paved the way for critical theories that laid stress on close reading of the text and objective study of a piece of art. In the present times when the content is often overshadowed or even devoured by varied contexts, Arnold's emphasis on timelessness

and autonomy of texts firmly establish the universality, permanence and constancy of great ideas and emotions irrespective of their circumstances.

Arnold advocated culture as a remedy of all social problems. He studied the impact of culture on society and argued that if a society lacks in conscious engagement with culture, it might lead to intellectual and moral leukaemia, the evidence of which he noticed in the narrowmindedness and conformity of the philistines. Culture, for Arnold was not just an individual concern to be addressed in isolation, but a social pursuit for perfection requiring concerted efforts of the entire society.

Perfection, as culture conceives it, is not possible while the individual remains isolated: the individual is obliged, under pain of being stunted and enfeebled in his own development if he disobeys, to carry others along with him in his march towards perfection, to be continually doing all he can to enlarge and increase the volume of the human stream sweeping thitherward. (Arnold 13-14)

Such a pursuit of culture could smoothen the differences between the diverse or even contrasting claims, help people rise over their petty self-interests and achieve a cohesion otherwise not possible. In the present era when countless divisive forces— religion, caste, creed, language, gender, social status, region, political affiliations and different cultural practices— threaten to create rifts among people and jeopardise communal peace and harmony, Arnold's perception of culture— conscious and continuous engagement with the higher or inner self— can certainly act as a unifying, pacifying and harmonizing force across the globe.

Arnold considered education a vehicle for culture. As an Inspector of Schools, he was brought into close contact with people from all sections of society. "This exposure revealed stark realities that deeply pained him: the Aristocracy's resistance to new ideas, the Philistines' superficial liberalism, and the Populace's pervasive ignorance" (qtd. in Gupta 26). Though he aimed at bringing "sweetness and light" to all sections of society and dispel the bitterness and gloom that prevailed over them, he was mainly concerned with the middle class, the section of society he himself belonged to. Dr. Gupta quotes G. Tillotson, "He set himself the task of refining that class 'the great representative of trade and dissent' of arnoldifying it; of endowing it with 'culture...by means of reading, observing and thinking" (Tillotson 47). He had a firm belief that culture could be transmitted only through education. As such a great responsibility lay in the hands of the educators, they must play a pivotal role in propagating culture through education that aligns with cultural pursuits. For this, he suggested liberal education, a system which was not confined to vocational training or professional skills of youngsters, but which was concerned with sharpening their critical faculties, developing wisdom and fostering empathy for their fellow beings. Arnold envisioned a system in which educators, acting as guides, ought to help and encourage students become ideal citizens by inculcating in them a sense of responsibility towards themselves and towards mankind. While STEM fields in education, on which too much emphasis is laid to the exclusion of humanities in today's digitally competitive era, certainly hone one's critical thinking and problem-solving skill and lead to innovation and creativity, they fail to develop wisdom and empathy. Wisdom and empathy are essential for shaping a balanced personality and can be nurtured only through humanities— academic disciplines that explore human experience, values, beliefs and practices across various cultures and societies as expressed in their art, literature and philosophy. Arnold's vision of liberal education is very pertinent in contemporary era to maintain global peace and harmony.

Relevance in Contemporary Society

One of the most vital concerns of the present era is the impact of widespread digitalisation on cognitive and emotional lives of human beings. Unchecked streaming services on social media and the continuous influx of information often leads to superficial engagement with it, causing difficulty in processing it and making effective decision based on it. Collini has described this infobesity as "distracted living". In a world where digital media often prioritises speed over depth, there is a growing need to revive the joy of sustained reading. Arnold believed in the transformative power of art and literature. Arnold's advice to devote oneself to "the best which has been thought and said" (Arnold ix) offers a true remedy out of this dilemma. When one takes time out of one's hectic schedule and immerses oneself into a well-chosen classic, one not only adds to one's knowledge, critical thinking and empathy for others but also develops a habit of reflection on universal themes like birth and death, love and loss, and struggle and resilience. He gradually forms a more balanced, broader, calmer and more accommodating outlook on life, counteracting the fragmenting shallowness that intrudes upon him banefully as he interacts digitally in this techno-savvy age.

The value of liberal arts in education, particularly in higher education, is being questioned again and again in an era given to material success and which is succumbing under economic pressure; the subjects like history, philosophy, art and literature are considered less relevant and useful in comparison to STEM fields which cater to material demands. But we should not ignore Arnold's appeal to integrate liberal arts in education, which has a humanistic approach to the complexities of life, which is rooted in the study of classics, and which inspires among scholars feeling of inquisitiveness, appreciation of divergent perspectives, and devotion to "pursuit of perfection...the pursuit of sweetness and light." (Arnold 47) By fostering such an interdisciplinary approach in education students will learn to arrive at informed decisions that are not merely materially gratifying but also empathetically, ethically and aesthetically fulfilling.

The ever-widening social, cultural and political polarization in today's world in the name of religion, culture, class, gender, language, traditions and customs is contributing to mutual mistrust, hatred, and tension in society and creating rifts among people belonging to different communities. Arnold's emphasis on shared cultural literacy offers a pathway to social cohesion (Hall). The communal divides can be bridged by putting into practice Arnold's belief in "shared cultural heritage and the universality of certain human experiences" (Geertz). This can be achieved by creating public spaces— public libraries, book clubs, e-libraries and other online platforms— where people from varying backgrounds may read, discuss and appreciate universal themes in the same works, as found, for instance, in Shakespeare's poetry and plays or in Wordsworth's poetry; these works evoke ideas and emotions that are common to one and all. This shared experience and appreciation can foster peaceful and respectful dialogue transcending partisan divides and realise the ideal of cohesive and harmonious society.

Methodology

The researcher employs a qualitative research methodology combining textual and contextual analysis. A close reading of the primary sources —selected works of Matthew Arnold, particularly *Culture and Anarchy*, poetry and critical writings serve as the basis to understand his concept of liberal humanism. The socio-cultural and historical context of England in the Victorian era will be analysed to ascertain their impact on the origin and development of these tenets. Secondary sources— literary critiques, historical texts and scholarly articles—are reviewed to ascertain their relevance in in the present context and underpin the findings.

Significance of The Study

Underscoring the transformative power of culture through education, Arnold's liberal humanism serves as a lens for educators, policymakers and leaders to reassess, reorient and broaden our narrow approach to education, culture and democracy and recalibrate our curricula to align with complex global changes in today's digital era, — an era characterized by rapid technological advancement, infobesity, cultural fragmentation, moral crisis and spiritual anaemia, — and further our efforts towards individual and societal excellence. The study is significant to ascertain the extent to which Arnold's ideals can be relevant to foster critical thinking and innovation along with empathy and quality public discourse, transcending distinctions of class and kind and achieve the long-cherished goal of enlightened, equitable and cohesive societies

Analysis

Matthew Arnold, an eminent poet, critic and educator of the Victorian era, was deeply concerned about disintegrating moral and intellectual fabric of the contemporary English society. Arnold lived in an age that was going through an unprecedented transformation. Scientific and technological advancement were giving huge push to industrialisation which led to expansion of business and foreign trade; people were becoming more and more materialistic, with little or no respect for religious, ethical and moral values. Age old traditions and conventions were being questioned, despised and thrown away disdainfully. Arnold was extremely aggrieved by what he called "Philistinism"— a narrow, materialistic mindset that prioritised commerce and routine over the higher pleasures of the intellect and spirit. He defined culture as "the best which has been thought and said," (Arnold ix) and it was only engagement with culture through education, particularly humanities and liberal arts, that the excesses of the commercially driven industrial life in modern times could be counterbalanced. It was only through exposure of people to "timeless values and ideas" that their lives could be elevated. These higher and more vital values had been neglected by them because of their excessive focus on material possessions; the only way to rediscover them was the study of philosophical and classical literature of the past. Arnold was not just diagnosing the ills of his contemporary society, he was prescribing cultural remedy for the upliftment of the nation as a whole; he was not merely a critique, but a visionary. For Arnold culture, "... is a *harmonious expansion of all the powers* which make the beauty and worth of human nature..." (Arnold 14). Culture requires the study of art and literature in unison, not in isolation; an integrated approach to life combining "experience" with "reflection" so that man could think deeply about himself, his society and the entire mankind.

Conclusion

In a pluralistic society, like ours, there is always a need for a revised and more inclusive approach— one that respectfully seeks insights from the past and blends with the diverse human experience of the present — to arrive at meaningful solutions to current and future problems and move forward in our endeavour to establish a more peaceful, harmonious, progressive and cohesive society. Matthew Arnold's concept of liberal humanism can prove a vital and powerful tool to address many of the issues and challenges in the contemporary era. Arnold's belief in culture as man's endless and strenuous journey towards perfection, his focus on pursuit of truth, beauty and wisdom as the most cherished goals of human life, his reliance in autonomy and timelessness of literary texts, his advocacy of liberal and humanistic education, and his insistence on promoting shared cultural heritage among people from diverse communities can certainly inculcate introspection, nurture philosophical contemplation, stimulate critical thinking, encourage peaceful and respectful dialogue, and contribute to social cohesion, communal peace and harmony, and sustainable development and progress in today's technologically and materially advanced but disjointed and fragmented world— a world where man is left stranded and destined to lead an isolated, disconnected and alienated life.

By revisiting Matthew Arnold's ideas, policymakers, educationists and leaders can work in unison to build a relevant and strong framework for creating a better world absorbed in elevated human experience. His appeal to espouse "the best which has been thought and said" (Arnold ix) can act as a catalyst, rekindling our dedication to pursuit of beauty, truth and wisdom, — whether through creation of public spaces for cultural reciprocity, promotion of classic art and literature, or making humanistic education mandatory in academia, — and smoothen our path, along with technological innovation and advancement, to a meaningful, connected, peaceful, empathetic, resilient, morally enlightened and fulfilling humane existence.

References

1. *Culture and Anarchy*. Project Gutenberg, 1 Aug. 2003, www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/4212.
2. Alexander, Edward. *Matthew Arnold and John Stuart Mill*. Routledge, 2014.
3. Collini, Stefan. *Culture and Anarchy and Other Writings*. Cambridge University Press, 1993
4. Gadamer, Hans-Georg. *Truth and Method*. Continuum, 1975.
5. Geertz, Clifford. *The Interpretation of Cultures*. Basic Books, 1973.
6. Gupta, N. K. Das, editor. "On Matthew Arnold." *Culture and Anarchy*, Lakshmi Narain Agarwal, Educational publishers, 1979.
7. Gupta, S. P. Sen, editor. Preface. *Matthew Arnold's Culture and Anarchy*, Prakash book Depot, 2nd edition, 1983. <https://prakashbookdepot.blogspot.com>
8. Hall, Stuart. *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. Sage Publications, 1997.
9. Rapple, Brendan A. *Matthew Arnold and English Education: The Poet's Pioneering Advocacy in Middle Class Instruction*. McFarland, 2005.
10. Tillotson, G. *Criticism and the Nineteenth Century*. 1951.
11. Trilling, Lionel. *Matthew Arnold*. Norton, 1939.